

The Role of Pronouns in Malay Grammar and Differences Usage of Pronouns between English and Malay Language

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Abstract. *In this scientific article describes the types of adjective that uses in the grammar of the malay language, their place in the sentence is clearly explained, and based on the findings, similarities and differences with the grammar of the english language are explained through opinions and analyzes.*

Key words: *malay language, uzbek language, types of adjective, grammar, adverbs, base, form.*

INTRODUCTION

Pronoun is a word that can replace noun or noun phrase, eliminating the need for repetition. Pronouns serve as a substitute for nouns, not only allowing for more efficient communication but also adding fluency and clarity to our daily communication. They can refer to majority of people, objects, places, or someones ideas, making them versatile tools in our everyday conversations and written texts ect. Malay pronouns include also personal pronouns (refer to the persons speaking in a daily life, the persons spoken to someone, or the persons or things spoken about), indefinite pronouns, relative pronouns (connect parts of sentences to each other) and reciprocal or reflexive pronouns (in which the object of a verb is being acted on by verb's subject). The usage of personal pronouns in Malay can be a bit confusing especially if you are new to Malay. This is because there are several words that carry the same meaning but the usage is different according to whom you are addressing or speaking to. An incorrect usage can make you come across as disrespectful, which is why we put extra emphasis on personal pronouns. Here are some English pronouns and their Malay equivalents:

PERSONAL PRONOUNS:

The following are the personal pronouns most commonly in use:

a) When addressing an inferior in rank or a *familiar friend*,

Singular, 1st *aku*

2nd *engkau*

3rd *dia or ia.*

Plural, 1st *kita or kami.*

2nd *kamu.*

3rd *dia, dia orang, or orang itu.*

When addressing a *superior*, or *an equal in rank*,

Singular, 1st *saya*

2nd *tuan*

3rd *dia* or *ia*

Plural, The same as above.

The personal pronoun *aku* is commonly used by Malays among themselves. Europeans use *saya* almost exclusively. *Kami* is but little used; it excludes the person addressed. The use of the 2nd person pronoun is avoided as far as possible. The name or rank, or the relation which the person addressed bears to the speaker, being substituted. Thus a Malay would say, "*John is a big boy,*" rather than "*You are a big boy.*" *ia* is seldom used in conversation. In writing, *ia* is generally used for the subject, and *dia* for the object. *Orang* added to the pronoun of the 3rd person forms the plural, but the plural need not be expressed unless ambiguity would arise from the use of the simple pronoun *dia*.

POSSESSIVE PRONOUNS.

Properly speaking the only possessive pronouns in Malay are the suffixes,

- a) **ku**, mine;
- b) **mu**, yours;
- c) **nya**, his or theirs. These are all joined by a hyphen to the noun expressing the thing possessed, as,
 - a) baju-*ku*, my coat
 - b) rumah-*mu*, your house
 - c) kuda-*nya*, his horse.

Of these only **-nya** is used in conversation; **-ku** and **-mu** being only used in written compositions. All personal pronouns become possessive pronouns when placed after the noun expressing the object possessed, or by the addition of the possessive particle *punya*, as explained above. When the substantive which the possessive pronoun qualifies is omitted or understood, or when the possessive pro- noun completes the predicate of a sentence, the form *punya* must be used, as,

- a) **dia-lah saya punya**, it is mine
- b) **rumah itu dia punya**, the house is his.

DEMONSTRATIVE PRONOUNS

The demonstrative pronouns in Malay are: *itu*, that, those; *ini*, this, these. They can both be used either as adjectives or as true pronouns; when used as adjectives they follow the noun which they qualify. Examples:

- a) **itu-lah dia**, that is he
- b) **anak ini**, this child. The following are also demonstrative pronouns, but cannot be used as adjectives:
 - c) **ia'itu, dia'itu**- they, that, the same.
 - a) **ia'ini**- this, this one. These forms are more emphatic than the above; examples:
 - b) *kuda kecil*- small horses
 - c) *ia'itu-lah baik*-(they) are the good ones
 - d) *ia'ini anak orang kaya*-this one is the rich man's child.

INTERROGATIVE PRONOUNS

The following are the interrogative pronouns, in Malay grammar:

- a) **apa**, what
- b) **siapa**, who
- c) **mana**, which, what
- d) **apa macham**, what kind of.

Only *mana*, and *apa macham* can be used as adjectives. *Mana* is also an adverb, meaning "where?" When used as an interrogative pronoun it must follow the noun. *Apa macham* may either precede or follow the noun. *Apa* and *siapa* cannot be joined to a noun.

THE RELATIVE PRONOUNS

The relative pronouns in Malay are:

1. **yang-** who, what, which, that
2. **mana-**yang, whichever
3. **barang yang-**what, that which
4. **barang apa-** what, whatever
5. **barang siapa-** he who, whoever

In Malay *yang* is often used between the noun and the adjective which qualifies it, where no relative pronoun is required in English, as, *orang yang baik*, a good man, literally, "a man who is good." Yang must be used before the adjective when the noun is a compound word, as, *tukang kayu yang pandai*, a clever carpenter.

REFLECTIVE PRONOUNS

Reflective pronouns in Malay are formed from the personal pronouns by the addition of *sendiri* or *diri*, self. **Sendiri** is placed after the pronoun, and **diri** before the pronoun, as *saya sendiri*, *diri saya*, *diri kita*, etc. *Sendiri* is more commonly used in conversation than *diri*.

Sendiri and *diri* sometimes stand by themselves. They are then impersonal and mean "one's self." In some cases the personal pronoun is understood but not expressed. The pronominal suffixes,

- a) *ku*, *-mu*, *-nya*, may be joined to either **sendiri** or **diri**, thus,
- b) *diri-nya*, or *sendiri-nya*, himself, his own.

The possessive case may be formed as usual by the use of *punya*, or by placing the reflective pronoun after the noun, as

rumah kita sendiri- our own house.

kita sendiri punya rumah - our own house.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, it can be noted that the scope of pronouns within the Malay grammar has rather complex and intricate aspects which are different from English grammar. The language of the Malays have a long standing tradition of respect and Islamic influences whereby reiterative forms, personal, possessive, demonstrative, interrogative, relative and reflexive, pronouns are prudently utilized out at the right way. Even, it should be noted, that while elders occupy the higher position with regard to the communicative act, particularly in politeness strategies, such situations seem rather less developed in English. The language in which the pronoun is expressed in Malay may however change depending on the formality and social relationship that exist for one to speak well. The comparison indicates that trying to comprehend these differences is significant as it helps enhance and facilitate multilingual communication as well as, the correct use of grammar. Another processing strategy resides into the awareness of these their distinction between both languages as they evolve and coexist.

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